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RECENT ADVANCES IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND MANAGEMENT OF DIABETIC NEUROPATHY

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes is a metabolic disorder of carbohydrate, fat, protein metabolism and it's a major health problem worldwide. Over last century change in human behaviour and lifestyle responsible for dramatically increased its incidences. Diabetic neuropathy is a microvascular and most common complication of Diabetes, characterized by pain in peripheral nervous system. DPN is difficult to detect due to its insidious onset and heterogeneous clinical manifestation. However early diagnosis is recommended and several clinical diagnosis methods are available such as clinical signs and symptoms, quantitative sensory and electro diagnostic testing, apart from that recently corneal confocal microscopy a new ophthalmic imaging technique is used for detection of small nerve fiber injury. Because DPN have multifactorial pathophysiology so current strategies for management of DPN is: symptomatic treatment, pathogenic treatment, reducing risk factors and glycaemic control.

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INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disorder in which body is not competent to accurately normalize blood sugar level. It's a highly prevalent and diverse metabolic disorder caused by occurrence of hyperglycaemia with disturbance of carbohydrate, fat and protein metabolism. Hyperglycaemia, glycosuria, hyperlipaemia, negative nitrogen balance and ketonaemia are the characteristics of Diabetic Mellitus. It is a leading cause of morbidity and a 5th leading cause of death in United State. The destructive call sound effect of hyperglycaemia are separated into Microvascular (such as diabetic neuropathy, nephropathy, retinopathy) and Macrovascular (such as coronary artery disease, peripheral disease & stroke) complications.

Diabetic neuropathy (DN) is a common and troublesome complication of diabetes mellitus and common among type 1 and 2 diabetic patients. Diabetes neuropathy may be yet detected at the time of diagnosis of type 2 diabetic patients¹. Diabetic neuropathy is a heterogeneous group of disorder that encompasses a wide range of abnormalities affecting proximal and distal peripheral sensory and motor nerves as well as the autonomic nervous system². The main symptoms the patient experiences vary from sensory disturbances with pain to muscle wasting³. Other symptoms are reduced sensation to sensory stimuli including pain, temperature, touch, and vibration in the feet and lower parts of the legs in diabetes patients is invariably a result of sensory neuropathy and may go unnoticed by patients for years unless specifically tested for and demonstrated¹.

The cause and consequences of diabetic neuropathy is very complex and not well understood. Several hypothesis have been postulated to understand the pathophysiology of diabetic neuropathy and include combination of increased oxidative stress, advanced glycation end point, polyol accumulation or polyol hyperactivity, decreased nitric oxide and impaired sodium⁺/potassium⁺ (Na⁺/K⁺)-adenosine triphosphate(ATPase)⁵.

30-40% of patients with diabetic neuropathy experience the symptoms of painful diabetic neuropathy. Commonly diabetic neuropathy is associated with distal symmetrical neuropathy affecting the lower limbs (especially toes and feet), and patients present with burning, stabbing, and tingling sensations. PDN is extremely distressing disease and significantly reduces the quality of life of patients. Hyperglycaemia is clearly important factor in the pathogenesis of nerve damage, and recent studies suggests that even minimal perturbations in blood glucose in those with impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) may lead to the development of small nerve fiber damage and neuropathic pain⁶.

Early diagnosis is the key factor for a better prognosis of Diabetic peripheral neuropathy and its diagnosis totally depend upon it, which further prevent diabetic foot ulcers, amputation, or disability. There is not a clearly established diagnostic test for DPN because of various pathophysiologies of DPN developing from nerve injury to clinical manifestation, different mechanism of different type of diabetes, comorbidities, and suspicious natural history of DPN. Therefore DPN remain challenging task for physician to screen, diagnosis, follow up, and evaluate for treatment purpose. In a busy clinic it is sufficient to establish whether an individual has symptoms, particularly of painful DPN and indeed through the use of a monofilament examination, whether or not the patient is at high risk of foot ulceration⁷. However, for the assessment of early nerve damage and more precise phenotyping of somatic and autonomic neuropathy, a large number of specialized screening and diagnostic tests are available such as Clinical signs and symptoms examination, Quantitative sensory testing, Sudomotor function, Neurophysiology, Skin Punch biopsy, Corneal confocal microscopy.

The possibilities to treat diabetic neuropathy are limited and a strict glycaemic control has mainly been advocated to treat diabetic neuropathy. The pathophysiology of diabetic neuropathy is complex and includes two major factors e.g. biochemical disturbances and vascular factors. In case of vascular factor of Diabetic neuropathy, the polyol pathway has been the target for pharmacological attention. Results obtained from experimental models and human studies and detailed knowledge of sorbitol pathways, which suggest that sorbitol, accumulates in peripheral nerve trunks, pharmacological substances were developed with the purpose to decrease sorbitol levels. Such aldose reductase inhibitors have in different studies shown promising results, but are still at a stage of development. Recently, various findings are emerging related to the management of diabetic neuropathy, as we know that an appropriate diagnosis is crucial and that the condition is not untreatable. Brain plasticity is a new treatment strategy for diabetic neuropathy⁹.

DIABETES AND DIABETIC PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY

DPN is the Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy in which pain sensation occur in peripheral nervous system due to dysfunction of peripheral nerves. DPN occur in both type 1 and type2 diabetes mellitus because of chronic hyperglycaemia. Its onset is usually insidious, so many patients remain asymptomatic for a long period of time, and patient complaints or routine screening examination often raise suspicion. Peripheral nerve fibers are classified into large myelinated A β fibers (proprioception, vibration, and pressure) and small thinly myelinated A δ fibers and unmyelinated C-fibers (warm and cold input with high threshold). DPN involves either or both the small and large nerve fibers in limbs in a length dependent manner. Small nerve fibers injuries occur earlier than large ones. In case of T1DM hyperglycaemia is a primary driver for nerve injuries whereas in case of T2DM factors other than hyperglycaemia are obesity, hypertension, low high density lipoprotein concentration and hypertriglyceridemia, which possibly contribute to nerve injuries¹⁰.

Diabetic Peripheral neuropathy is a highly complex and prevalent disease. Over 8% of the population has peripheral neuropathy and this number increases to 15% in individuals 40 years of age or older. The most common causes of peripheral neuropathy are prediabetes and type2 diabetes. At least half of all diabetic patients, including patients with type 1 diabetes, develop some form of neuropathy during their life time¹².

Diabetes can produce several type of peripheral nervous system (PNS) damage. The most common type of nerve damage is bilateral and symmetric damage to nerves of feet, with a distal to proximal gradient of severity, known as a stocking glove neuropathy. Because this pattern of nerve injury is so common, this neuropathy is synonymously called diabetic neuropathy. DN is primarily a disorder of sensory nerves, and, early in the course of DN, patients commonly experience positive sensory symptoms in the feet such as pain, tingling, and prickling sensations (paresthesias) as well as negative symptoms such as numbness; disordered sensory processing may evoke pain when the feet are touched (allodynia) and increased sensitivity to noxious stimuli (hyperalgesia)¹³.

Peripheral Nervous System Structure and Function

The PNS consists of 12 cranial nerves and 31 pairs of spinal nerves, and, similar to the CNS, the PNS is composed of both neurons and supporting glia, specifically Schwann cells (SCs) in PNS. Efferent axons from motor neurons carry information from CNS to muscles and glands, whereas afferent axons from sensory neurons carry information from peripheral sensory receptors to the CNS. In PNS, there are thin (<1 μ m) unmyelinated axons known as C fiber axons or small fibers. These axons are engulfed by and associated with non-myelinated SCs in a pattern reminiscent of axon-glia interactions in invertebrates and are grouped as "Remark bundles" when viewed in cross section. C fibers carry information from the autonomic nervous system as well as afferent impulses in response to temperature and noxious stimuli such as potentially injurious chemicals, extreme temperature and mechanical forces that cause tissue damage. In addition to unmyelinated C fiber, small myelinated A δ fibers subserving cold detection and high threshold mechanoreceptors are designated small afferent fibers. Essential to our ability to perceive pain, congenital loss of small fibers leads to ulcers, digital mutilation, and amputations¹³.

METHODS FOR DIAGNOSIS OF DIABETIC PRIPHERAL NEUROPATHY

There are several methods for diagnosis of peripheral diabetic neuropathy; clinical signs and symptoms, Quantitative sensory testing, sudomotor function, neurophysiology, skin punch biopsy, corneal confocal microcopy.

The onset of DPN is heralded by sensory symptoms that start in the toes and then progress proximally to involve the feet and legs in a stocking distribution. When the disease is well established in the lower limbs in more severe cases, there is upper limb involvement, with a similar progression proximally starting in fingers. As the disease advances, clear motor manifestations, such as wasting of the small muscles of the hands and limb weakness, become apparent. Crucially, sometimes there is sensory loss, which the patient might not be aware of and the first presentation of might be a foot ulcer. Approximately one third of neuropathic subjects experience a progressive build-up of unpleasant sensory symptoms in the lower limbs including tingling (paraesthesia), pain (burning, shooting, lancinating or arching in character), allodynia (contact pain) or unusual sensations (such as feeling of swelling of the feet or coldness of the legs when clearly the lower limbs look and feel fine, odd sensations on walking linked to "walking on hot sands" etc.) DPN is characteristically more severe at night and often disturb sleep, functionality (e.g. Ability to maintain work), mood and quality of life of diabetic patient. Depressive symptoms as a result of unremitting pain are common¹⁴.

CLINICAL DIAGNOSIS OF DIABETIC PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY

Damage to small sensory nerve fibers is one of the earliest manifestations of DPN and may be accompanied by continuous or episodic pain.

Symptoms and signs

The Douleur Neuropathique en 4 (DN4) includes questions for different types of neuropathic pain such as burning, painful cold, electrical shocks, tingling, pins and needles, numbness, and itching and a physical exam to test for touch and pin hypoaesthesia tactile dynamic allodynia and shown excellent sensitivity(83%) and specificity(90%) for neuropathic pain. The Leeds Assessment of neuropathic symptoms and signs (LANSS) scale is similar, elicits five symptoms and two signs of DPN has a comparable sensitivity and specificity. Other screening tests include the neuropathic pain Questionnaire (NPQ) (12 questions), The Neuropathic Pain Symptoms Inventory (NPSI) (12 questions), The Neurological symptoms Score (NSS) (17 questions), Diabetic Neuropathy Symptom (DNS) Score (17 questions). These are all interview based assessments of sensory, motor and autonomic deficits, with moderate sensitivity and specificity. Based on outcome a score of 6 to 8 denotes mild neuropathy, 9to11 moderate, and ≥ 12 severe neuropathy.¹⁶

Quantitative sensory testing

Quantitative sensory testing can be used to detect small and large nerve fiber function. Commercially available devices include CASE IV, The thermoesthesiometer, the biothesiometer, and the TSA II Neurosensory Analyser. These devices create temperature and vibratory stimuli and rely on the subject's response to define sensory thresholds. QST is painless and non-invasive, requires minimal training and is relatively easy to perform, which make it an attractive option to diagnose neuropathy.¹⁶

Diabetic autonomic neuropathy (Sudomotor function)

Diabetic autonomic neuropathy may affect a number of different organ systems including the cardiovascular, gastrointestinal, and genitourinary and sudomotor systems. Cardiovascular autonomic neuropathy is clinically most important form of DAN and is associated with abnormalities of heart rate control and vascular dynamics. Clinical manifestations of CAN include resting tachycardia, exercise intolerance, silent myocardial ischemia, and orthostatic hypotension. CAN assess by time domain heart rate response to deep breathing, Valsalva manoeuvre and change in posture. Gastrointestinal autonomic neuropathy affects gastrointestinal motor and sensory control and leads to esophageal dysmotility, gastroparesis, constipation, diarrhoea, and faecal incontinence; it can be assessed by Diabetes Bowel Symptom Questionnaire.

Sudomotor dysfunction may be one of the earliest manifestations of DAN resulting in loss of sweating and can be evaluated via several modalities. The quantitative sudomotor axon reflex test evaluates postganglionic axonal integrity, while the sympathetic skin response assesses polysynaptic pathways. The sweat indicator plaster (Neuropad) is a visual test, which uses a timed colour change to define the integrity of skin sympathetic cholinergic innervation. The thermoregulatory sweat test is a method of assessing location specific alterations by delivering a controlled heat stimulus to induce a generalized sweat response. The patient response is detected by assessing a significant colour change in cornstarch, sodium carbonate, or alizarin red, which are applied uniformly over the body. Sudoscan test assesses electrochemical skin conductance as an indicator of sweat gland function and can differentiate patients with and without neuropathy and controls with high sensitivity and specificity as well as patients with and without CAN.¹⁷

Neurophysiology

Nerve conduction studies are considered to be the gold standard for the diagnosis of DPN. Toronto consensus recommended the use of abnormal NCS with symptom or signs to diagnose DPN. The typical electrophysiological findings in DPN are amplitude reduction of the compound muscle action potential, slowing of sensory and motor NCV, prolonged F-wave latency and an absent Hoffman reflex. Although NCS provide an objective means of quantifying peripheral large nerve fiber dysfunction it cannot assess small sensory fiber damage, earliest manifestation of DPN. Another major limitation of NCS is poor reproducibility and lack of measurement standardization across the centres.

Several studies have reported NCS abnormalities in patient with impaired glucose intolerance (IGT) and DM. Glycaemic control, DM duration; age, male gender, and height are associated with electro diagnostic abnormalities in DM patients.¹⁷

Skin Biopsy

Skin biopsy allows morphometric quantification of intra epidermal nerve fibers (IENFs), expressed as the number of IENFs per length of section (IENF/mm). This technique has good reproducibility and an accurate quantification method has been established for assessing IENF pathology along with normative age matched. There is an age and sex related decline in IENFD, but unlike neurophysiology it is not affected by weight and height. The European Federation of Neurological Societies has published guidelines on its use in diagnosis of peripheral neuropathies. However the diagnostic yield of skin biopsy depends on the reference and cut off values selected and the definition of small fiber neuropathy.

Several studies have shown loss of IENFD in people with DM and IGT compared to healthy controls. Therefore the assessment of IENFD is a valid measure of diabetic neuropathy and may also be useful in predicting the development of clinical neuropathy. Recent studies showed a reduction in IENFD in patient with T2DM over 5 years, due to slower nerve regeneration in people with diabetes. Because IENFD is considered to be gold standard for the evaluation small fiber neuropathy it has been advocated as a measure of treatment response in clinical trials. However skin biopsy is an invasive technique, which requires experience and expertise to perform reliable IENFD staining with protein gene product 9.5 and subsequent quantification. The chance of bleeding and infection in DM patients also reduces its appeal as a diagnostic test for DPN and it therefore cannot be recommended in longitudinal and intervention studies.¹⁶

Corneal Confocal Microscopy

Corneal confocal microscopy is a non-invasive and relative ophthalmic imaging technique, which allows in vivo examination of cornea. The primary application of CCM was in diagnosis and management of corneal disease. However, in the early 2000s two landmark studies by Rosenberg et al and Malik et al reported a progressive loss of corneal sub basal nerve fibers in patients with increasing severity of DPN. Subsequently multiple centres have confirmed these finding in different population and the use of CCM to study DPN and neurodegeneration more broadly has grown exponentially.

The cornea is one of the most densely innervated tissues of the human body receiving sensory innervation from trigeminal ganglion.

The type of CCM used, i.e., white light or laser can significantly impact on image acquisition process and quality. Over the last decade, the vast majority of research centres have utilized the laser CCM (Heidelberg Retina Tomograph III Rostock Corneal Module; Heidelberg Engineering GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany) due to its superior image quality and rapid scanning time. In healthy cornea the nerve fibers are equally distributed while in DPN there is clustering of nerve fibers occurs.

Reduced corneal sensation in diabetes as a result of polyneuropathy was reported as early as 1974. In early 2000s, Rosenberg et al showed sub basal nerve alterations using CCM in patients with clinically confirmed DPN and Malik et al showed that the severity of corneal nerve pathology was related to DPN severity. CCM can be used to detect early corneal nerve alterations with excellent reproducibility between examiners, occasions and quantification method.¹⁸

MANAGEMENT APPROACH FOR DIABETIC PERIPHERAL NEUROPATHY

Current strategies for the treatment of diabetic peripheral neuropathy are based on;

- (i) Improving glycolic control and reducing other risk factors for the development of polyneuropathy.
- (ii) Symptomatic treatment of diabetic peripheral neuropathy.
- (iii) Treatment based on pathogenic mechanisms.
- (iv) Treatment of foot, autonomic and other complications.¹⁹

Improving Glycaemic Control and Reducing Other Risk Factors for Diabetic Peripheral Neuropathy

In the Rochester Diabetic neuropathy study Cohort, where clinical parameters and NC tests were used, the prevalence of DPN was 54% in patients with Type 1 diabetes and 45% in patients with Type 2 diabetes. Where NC tests were not used, clinic and population based studies showed surprisingly similar prevalence rates for DPN, affecting approximately 30% of all diabetic people. In EUROPEAN Prospective Complications study, where 3250 type 1 patients from 16 European countries involved in study, and a prevalence rate of 28% for DPN at baseline founded, which is closely and very strongly related to poor glycaemic control. The follow up study also showed that over a 7 year period, approximately one quarter of type 1 diabetic patients developed DPN; with age, duration of diabetes and poor glycaemic control being major factors. The development of neuropathy was also associated with potentially modifiable cardiovascular risk factors, such as hypertension, hyperlipidaemia, obesity and cigarette smoking. Recently other studies have also implicated cardiovascular risk factors, such as obesity, triglycerides in pathogenesis of DPN.

Based on recent epidemiological studies, correlates of DPN include increasing age, increasing duration of diabetes, poor glycaemic control, retinopathy, albuminuria and vascular risk factors. In type 2 diabetes, waist circumference, peripheral arterial disease and increasing age were found to be significant risk factors for development of DPN. DPN is also a major risk factor (predictor) for mortality, even more so than microalbuminuria and HbA1c.

The Diabetes Control and Complications Trial (DCCT) conclusively showed that intensive diabetes control could both prevent and retard the development of DPN and autonomic neuropathy. Current good clinical practice remains to intensively manage hyperglycaemia and other cardiovascular risk factors as part of the overall management of patients with DPN.¹⁹

Advances in the Symptomatic Treatment of DPN

Epidemiological data on DPN are limited. The prevalence of DPN based on one population based study was 16%, as assessed by a structured questionnaire and examination. Among these patients 12.5% had never reported symptoms to their doctor for DPN and 39% had never received treatment for their pain. In a more recent population based study, the overall prevalence of DPN was staggeringly high affecting approximately one in four diabetic subjects. Thus despite being common, DPN continues to be underdiagnosed and undertreated.

Severity of neuropathic pain can be assessed by the visual analogue scale (VAS), or the numerical rating scale (NRS), such as the 11-point Likert scale (0 no pain, 10 worst possible pain), which has been most widely used in recent DPN clinical trials. Several validated scales and Questionnaires including the brief pain inventory, the neuropathic pain symptoms inventory, the neuropathic pain questionnaire, the McGill pain questionnaires and so on can also be used.

Managing DPN in clinical practice can be a clinically challenging problem. However past decade, new and effective compounds have undergoes clinical trials and are already being used in clinical practice.

Tricyclic Antidepressants

Several randomized controlled trails have shown the efficacy of tricyclic antidepressants (TCA) in DPN. However TCA also have many side effects including anticholinergic effects, such as dry mouth, sweating, sedation and dizziness. Treatment is ideally started with small dose (10mg) of either amitriptyline or imipramine at night, as there is nocturnal exacerbation of painful symptoms and these antidepressants will assist with sleep. The dose can then be gradually titrated depending on adverse events and efficacy. Care should be taken not to exacerbate symptoms of postural hypotension. Such as dizziness, in those with autonomic neuropathy. In addition, recent data from a retro prospective study including 58,956 person years follow up on TCA therapy show an increased risk of sudden cardiac death associated with TCA doses in excess of 100mg/day. This is a major argument against the use of TCA in diabetic patients with cardiovascular disease.²⁰

Serotonin Noradrenaline R-uptake Inhibitors

Serotonin noradrenaline re-uptake inhibitors (SNRI), such as duloxetine, relieve pain by increasing synaptic availability of 5-hydroxytryptamine (5-HT) and noradrenaline in the descending pathways that are inhibitory to pain impulses. The efficacy of duloxetine in DPN has been investigated in three identical trials and pooled data from these shows that the 60mg/kg and 120mg/kg doses are effective in relieving painful symptoms, starting within a week. Efficacy was maintained throughout the treatment period of 12 weeks and 45-55% of patients achieved $\geq 50\%$ pain reduction.

A particular advantage of Duloxetine is there is no weight gain during prolonged treatment of up to a year. The most frequent adverse effects of duloxetine include nausea, somnolence, dizziness, constipation, dry mouth and reduced appetite. These adverse events are usually mild to moderate and transient. To reduce the chance of adverse events, clinical experience suggests a starting dose of 30mg/day for approximately a week. It might be helpful to advise the patient to take the medication with food or after food.

Venlafaxine at a dose of 150-225 mg/kg is also effective in relieving DPN, although clinically significant electrocardiogram changes have been reported as adverse events. This is major concern, as many diabetic patients have coexistent cardiac disease.¹⁹

Anticonvulsants

Gabapentin and Pregabalin bind to the α -2- δ subunit of the calcium channel, reducing calcium flux and thus resulting in reduced neurotransmitter release in the hyper excited neuron. Gabapentin is well established treatment for DPN, although the doses in clinical practice are much lower than the dose used in main clinical trial of up to 3600mg/day.

Evidence for efficacy of pregabalin in DPN is even better, as there have been several clinical trials in DPN that showed its efficacy compared with placebo. One study examined a combined analysis of six controlled trials of 5-12 weeks duration, and found 39% and 46% of patients with DPN treated with pregabalin 300 and 600mg/day, respectively, achieved at least 50% pain relief. Pregabalin is licensed for management of DPN. The most frequent side effects are dizziness, somnolence, and peripheral oedema, headache, and weight gain.²⁰

Opioid Agonists

The weak opiate derivative, tramadol, has been found to be effective in relieving neuropathic pain. Another opioid, oxycodone slow release, has also been shown to be effective in the management of neuropathic pain. Traditionally, clinicians have been rather conservative in the use of opioid agonists, prescribing them as an add-on to other therapy, although clinical evidence to support this approach is somewhat limited. In one cross-over study, low dose combination therapy with gabapentin and morphine was significantly more effective than either monotherapy at a higher dose. However combination therapy was associated with a higher frequency of adverse effects than monotherapy. Prolonged-release oxycodone was also found to enhance the effects of existing gabapentin therapy in patients with DPN. More recently, the combination of nortriptyline and gabapentin was found to be superior to either treatment on its own.²¹

Topical capsaicin

Topical capsaicin works by depleting substance p from nerve terminals, and there might be worsening of neuropathic symptoms for the first 2-4 weeks of application. Topical capsaicin (0.075%) applied sparingly 3-4 times per day to the affected area has also been found to relieve neuropathic pain.

Lacosamide

Lacosamide is a sodium channel modulator and a promising treatment for DPN. In the phase II study, lacosamide was found to be beneficial in relieving DPN. Phase III, placebo controlled trials are now required to evaluate its efficacy, both on its own or as a combination treatment with another effective agent.

α -Lipoic Acid

Infusion of the anti-oxidant α -lipoic acid at a dose of 600mg i.v. per day over a 3 week period has been found to be useful in reducing neuropathic pain. A meta-analysis including 1258 patients from four prospective trials showed that treatment with α -lipoic acid (600mg/day) for 3 weeks was associated with a significant and clinically meaningful improvement in a positive neuropathic symptoms (pain, burning, paraesthesia and numbness), as well as neuropathic deficits. For 5 weeks treatment of α -lipoic acid improved neuropathic symptoms and decrease the patients of DPN, because α -lipoic acid is orally active drug. An oral dose of 600mg once daily appears to provide the optimum risk to benefit ratio, but a confirmatory larger trial might be required.¹⁹

Treatment Algorithm

A recent consensus meeting evaluated the trial evidence for the various pharmacological treatments for DPN and suggested a treatment algorithm. The panel compared the relative efficacy and safety of treatments for DPN and recommended that a TCA, SNRI or a α -2- δ agonist should be considered for first line treatment. On the basis of trial data, duloxetine would be the preferred SNRI and pregabalin would be the preferred α -2- δ agonist. Initial selection of treatment will be influenced by the assessment of contraindications, consideration of comorbidities and costs; for example, in diabetic patients with the history of heart disease, elderly patients on other concomitant medications such as diuretics and antihypertensive, patient with comorbid orthostatic hypotension and so on, TCA have relative contraindications. In patient with liver disease, duloxetine should not be prescribed, and in those with edema, pregabalin or gabapentin should be avoided. If pain is inadequately controlled, depending on contraindications, a different first line agent might be considered.

A combination of first line therapies might be considered if there is pain, despite a change in first line monotherapy. If pain is inadequately controlled, opioids such as tramadol and oxycodone might be added in a combination treatment.²⁰

Figure: Treatment Algorithm for Diabetic Neuropathy Pain; SNRI: Serotonin Noradrenaline Reuptake Inhibitor; TCA: Tricyclic Antidepressant.²¹

Non pharmacological Treatments

Lack of response and unwanted side-effects of conventional drug treatments force many sufferers to try alternative therapies, such as acupuncture, near infrared phototherapy, low intensity laser intensity laser therapy and transcutaneous electrical stimulation, frequency modulated electromagnetic neural stimulation (FREMS) therapy, high frequency external muscle stimulation and as a last resort, implantation of an electrical spinal cord stimulator. Unfortunately, most of the studies involving non-pharmacological agents are uncontrolled and there is need for randomized controlled trails in this respect.

Treatment based on pathogenic mechanisms

In experimental diabetes several studies examining a number of abnormalities related to the pathogenesis of DPN such as, including increased advanced glycation end-point formation, polyol pathway hyperactivity, oxidative stress, and alteration in protein kinase C (PKC)- β pathway through diacylglycerol.

There is now a consensus that the aetiology of DPN is probably multifactorial. Several compounds including several aldose reductase inhibitors ARI, the antioxidant α -lipoic acid, PKC- β inhibitors ruboxistaurine and two ACE inhibitors targeting these abnormal pathways have undergone clinical trials. Only the ARI, epalrestat and antioxidant α -lipoic acid are in clinical use.¹⁹

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